

Research Article

Literature Appreciation Learning Innovation Using Blended Learning Model to Students of MTS Al Ma'had An-Nur Bantul Amidst The Covid-19 Pandemic

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Abstract: The COVID-19 pandemic has become a disruption that has shocked all Indonesian people. It is not only disturbing but also has an impact on all activities, especially learning activities. Learning activities that were originally carried out face-to-face have now become distance learning. Learning innovation needs to be carried out to overcome distance learning during this COVID-19 pandemic. The problem of literary appreciation does not only occur during the COVID-19 pandemic. The problem of literary appreciation learning has always had problems with the innovations used by teachers. This study aims to overcome the problem of lack of innovation in literary appreciation learning. The blended learning model is chosen to be applied in maximizing literary appreciation learning for MTS Al Ma'had An-Nur students. This type of research uses descriptive qualitative research. Data collection techniques are in the form of document analysis, interviews and observations.

Keywords: Literary Appreciation Learning, Blended Learning Model, COVID-19 Pandemic.

Introduction

Learning Indonesian is very important given at all levels of education. Sheets of Indonesia is a language that everyone is able to use. The importance of learning Indonesia is aimed at improving student's ability to communicate both orally and in writing. In addition, the use of Indonesian that is taught properly can support students confidently speaking in public. Keep in mind that there are four skills learned in Indonesia, namely: writing, listening, reading, and speaking. These four skills are important factors for students to maximize their potential. Likewise, in Indonesia language learning, there are literary appreciation learning subjects.

In Indonesian language subject, literature appreciation learning must be given starting from elementary school to university level. Literature appreciation learning is a learning activity so that students get to know more, understand, appreciate and be able to apply the positive things contained in literary works in everyday life. Literature appreciation learning is one of the important lessons learned at all school levels. Students can get to know more about literature. Hidayati (2014) explained that literature appreciation is an activity related to sharpening feelings, reasoning and imagination, as well as sensitivity to society, culture and environment.

Literature appreciation is also related to reading literary works accompanied by genuine appreciation. The results of reading will lead to a good appreciation of literary works and understanding the moral values in it. Sensitivity and concern for the values of life, especially humanity, lead to empathy and tolerance among human beings (Al-Ma'ruf and Farida, 2017: 25).

Based on the explanation, it can be concluded that literature appreciation is learning that requires a serious understanding and appreciation of the literary works in order to gain new insights and apply them in our daily life.

Literature appreciation learning is not focused on only one literary work but all types of literary works. Various literary works that exist and can be found in literature learning for junior high school students are poetry, drama, fairy tales, legends and short stories. Teachers must always be ready to provide learning in any condition, especially amidst COVID-19 pandemic. Learning amidst COVID-19 pandemic certainly creates several obstacles in the learning and teaching process. However, this must be addressed by teachers and students wisely. All obstacles in the existing learning process can definitely be overcome.

COVID-19 pandemic is a catastrophe that has affected the entire world. The impact of COVID-19 is very unfavourable, especially in the education aspect. Education in Indonesia has undergone several changes in the learning process which was originally carried out face-to-face in schools to online learning. The Ministry of Education and Culture (2020) stated that the policy of implementing online-based learning is an official directive from the Ministry of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia which recommends that all education units in Indonesia, without exception, to heed efforts to prevent the spread of COVID-19 by implementing social restrictions and eliminating present learning.

The Minister of Education has issued Circular Letter Number 3 of 2020 concerning Prevention of COVID-19 to the Education Unit which states that schools and universities are closed. This is done to break the chain of the spread of COVID-19, instead the teaching and learning process is replaced online for all levels of education. It can be concluded that teaching and learning activities that were originally carried out face to face (present) must be limited to online program. Thus, all learning activities depend on the use of information technology. The information technology can be accessed through the device. The gadgets can be mobile phones, tablets and laptops.

The use of information technology with proper access can be useful to assist the process of learning activities. Amidst COVID-19 pandemic, teachers must be more enthusiastic to be creative by utilizing increasingly advanced technology for learning innovation, especially literature appreciation learning. New innovations to create effective, smooth and even not boring learning must be thought out carefully by the teacher. Innovations that can be used by teachers can be by using learning media, learning models, learning strategies, and many more. The results of the use of new innovations in learning are expected to produce right learning objectives.

Online teaching and learning activities should not be used as an excuse for teachers not to be more creative in order to support the distance learning process so that it remains effective and maximal. This learning process is carried out by teachers and students to do with online meeting and so are the assignments. Therefore, the most important point is that in learning literature appreciation learning, one of the right learning model innovations is chosen to support maximum learning outcomes. The learning model used is a blended learning model. Although this online learning poses a number of obstacles, the readiness of teachers and students, learning support facilities and internet access can be overcome gradually.

Research Methods

This research uses qualitative research. Creswell (2015:34) suggested that in qualitative research, the researcher collects data from participants in the study and develops a form to record during the research. In addition, qualitative research is a research that produces analytical procedures that do not use statistical analysis procedures or other quantification methods (Moleong, 2010:6). Furthermore, this study uses a descriptive method to describe the conditions that occurred during research activities.

This research was conducted at MTS Al Ma'had An-Nur which is located at Jalan Ngrukem, Sawah Area, Pendowoharjo, Sewon District, Bantul Regency. The subjects of this study were an Indonesian language teacher and 38 students of class VII A. While the object of this research is the use of blended learning model in literature appreciation learning. Collecting data in the research in the form of observations and interviews with an Indonesian language teacher and several students. Observation and interview methods are useful for knowing the conditions experienced by teachers or students when learning activities take place.

Discussion

1) The Importance of Literature Appreciation Learning for Junior High School Students

Literature appreciation learning is very important to be taught at all levels of education units, especially at the junior high school level. Literary works taught in the form of poetry, fairy tales, legends, dramas, and short stories. Each literary learning material has a different way of appreciating it. However, all of them have the same goal, namely the process of understanding, interpreting thoroughly which in the end students will be able to give awards in the form of assessments. In fact, students can also find out new insights and life values that they can implement in a social environment.

Literature appreciation learning aims to make students understand thoroughly, appreciate and give awards for a literary work. Sunahrowi (2016: 184) explained the importance of literature appreciation learning which is closely related to learning about life. Through literary works we will gain new knowledge, insights and important components that can improve our minds. The dark sides of life can be better because of the practice of the values contained in a literary work.

Literature appreciation learning aims for the creative process of students in providing an assessment after enjoying and living a literary work. Students have different thoughts and understandings of the process of appreciating literature. However, this is not something that can be disputed or blamed, because these differences will provide new insights. It can even complement the understanding and thinking of students in the learning process of appreciation of a literary work.

Literature appreciation learning taught by teachers to students, especially to the junior high school students can add new insights and experiences to literature. Students can find out their new knowledge through the provision of material by the teacher. They can use other reference sources to get new insights and even examples of the application of literature appreciation. This literature appreciation also fosters interest in reading literary works. With the development of increasingly advanced technology, we can also learn how to appreciate literature through media such as contents on YouTube. Literature appreciation learning is not all done by reading alone but can be through watching and even listening to a literary work.

2) Literature Appreciation Learning Problems of MTS Al Ma'Had An-Nur Students

In education field, especially in the learning process, there are certainly different problems. This problem is a challenge for teachers. Teachers must be able to face and even improve the quality of the learning process. Teachers also have to be more creative to find the right solution for a better learning process. There are several problems in literature appreciation learning of MTS Al Ma'Had An-Nur students. There are two important points in the problem of the literature appreciation learning process, these problems were obtained from the results of observations and interviews with an Indonesian language teacher and students of class VII A.

First, the problem of literature appreciation learning has existed for a long time (before the COVID-19 pandemic). The literature appreciation learning innovation used by the teacher is less creative. The teacher taught with a lecture learning model only. In fact, the use of technology that is increasingly developing is still not maximized in literature appreciation learning. This makes students of class VII A in MTS Al Ma'Had An-Nur feel bored easily during the learning process.

Students also become less concentrated in understanding the material presented by the teacher because the literature appreciation learning is monotonous. Teachers should be more creative and innovative in using learning models, so that problems in learning can be resolved properly.

Second, the problem in literature appreciation learning amidst COVID-19 pandemic is actually almost the same as the learning problem in the first point. Teachers are still not optimal in using and choosing learning models. The difference is that the current condition is a pandemic. Learning that was originally done at school (face to face) is now distance learning or online. This adds the obstacles in literature appreciation learning. The important point that becomes a learning obstacle is the use of less creative learning models.

Class VII A consist of 38 male students and they have their own way of learning. Moreover, in the condition of distance learning, teachers cannot fully monitor the learning activity. However, if the teacher uses a creative learning model with the help of technology, it is hoped that the 38 students will not be completely bored while learning. The learning model chosen is the blended learning model that combines online and offline learning. The creation of the use of the learning model is expected to be able to overcome problems or obstacles in the process of literature appreciation learning.

3) Blended Learning Model in Literature Appreciation Learning of MTS Al Ma'Had An-Nur Students

An important point in the blended learning model is to combine face to face activities and online classes. The application of learning using this model is very useful for reducing present learning (Hidayat, *et al.*, 2020:403). This blended learning model is useful for complementing distance learning with conventional learning. Blended learning model or mixed learning is a solution to overcome the weaknesses of distance learning (Noer, 2010).

Yuliati and Saputra (2020) stated that learning amidst COVID-19 pandemic has become very varied, there are various learning models used today including online methods, offline methods, face to face, home visits, blended learning and others. One of the learning models that can be done in current conditions is a combination learning model or what is known as blended learning, because it is considered capable of forming and developing students independent learning.

Pujiasih (2020) stated that learning using blended learning model will be able to improve optimal learning outcomes because in this learning process there is a shift in learning that initially was all teacher-centred, now becomes student-centred. From the explanations of some of these expert opinions, it can be concluded that the blended learning model can overcome the problems of the teaching and learning process amidst COVID-19 pandemic. This discussion focuses on literature appreciation learning for students of class VII A in MTS Al Ma'had An-Nur who are advised to use the blended learning model. This model is very effective to use because it is able to overcome the problems of the teaching and learning process which was originally face to face, but now has to go online.

In literature appreciation learning using blended learning model, there are two learning activities. Learning by going offline through WhatsApp group and google classroom. Then, for online learning, they can use Google Meet and YouTube contents provided by the teacher. This learning certainly uses devices for the learning process and doing the tasks given by the teacher. In the blended learning model, there are three stages of learning that must be done. Grant (2001) stated that basically in the blended learning model there are three basic stages that must be carried out in a learning. These stages are interrelated, namely: seeking of information, acquisition of information and synthesizing of knowledge. The first stage, Seeking of Information, in this activity is online learning, students are asked to join google meet. The link had been shared in the WhatsApp group, they were asked to listen and understand the teacher's explanation regarding the literature

appreciation learning material of fable or legend texts. The teacher provided an initial understanding in learning and later if something was not clear, students could ask questions in the forum. Furthermore, for offline learning activities, the teacher assigned students to look for material about literature appreciation learning of fable or legend texts and they could write them down on a concept map. It aimed to make students more aware of the literary appreciation material. Students could find information related to the material in online sources. They could also ask about literary appreciation material through WhatsApp group that had been provided.

The second stage, Acquisition of Information, the learning process is through online discussion activities on google meet. This activity is to briefly discuss the concept map tasks that students have been working on. The teacher also asked some students to present their assignments in a discussion forum. Other students could ask questions and responded to their friends' presentations. The third stage, Synthesizing Knowledge is a learning activity in the final stage. In this process, after students clearly knew the material about literature appreciation learning given by the teacher and the results of the creativity of concept maps that have been made by students, the teacher provided the final stage of learning. The teacher gave examples of YouTube contents on how to appreciate literature in the form of fable or legend texts that can be done by reading and retelling. This learning was carried out offline and students were also assigned to look for learning contents on YouTube with other sources as exemplified by the teacher.

Furthermore, the teacher also assigned students to carry out the last stage of literature appreciation, namely rereading fable or legend texts such as the YouTube content that the teacher provided. This assignment was in the form of a video, students were expected to be creative in doing assignments. This assignment was collected in the google classroom class.

Literature appreciation learning activities in the form of fable or legend texts with blended learning models aim to make students not bored in learning. Moreover, all male students of class VII A certainly have different understandings and ways from female students. In addition, in this blended learning model, the teacher hopes that students will be more focused and can understand learning even at a distance. In addition to the teacher providing examples of YouTube contents to support learning, students are also expected to be able to learn independently by maximizing the use of information technology to complete the tasks given by the teacher. During this pandemic condition, there is no reason that both teachers and students are lacking in honing their respective creativity. Teachers use learning innovations assisted by blended learning models that can be used as creative breakthroughs to provide learning that is in accordance with the desired learning objectives.

4) Social Media Content in Literature Appreciation Learning of MTS Al Ma'Had An-Nur Students

In literature appreciation learning in the form of fable or legend texts with this blended learning model and social media is also assisted. Skills in choosing social media as a learning supporter for this blended learning model are very important. The selection of this social media must be really selective. The selected social media must be avoided from indecent things. It should increase new knowledge, new experiences, and new skills so that students are also encouraged to be creative and students can maximize the knowledge they want. Students understand how much new knowledge and skills are needed from social media exemplified by the teacher. Especially amidst COVID-19 pandemic, there are certainly many contents on social media that are up to date and familiar to students.

Social media contents such as on YouTube are the right solution for the implementation of the blended learning model in the appreciation of fable or legend texts learning. The blended learning model and the social media used in the chosen learning are expected to maximize the literature appreciation learning process. On YouTube, there are a lot of creative contents as examples of literature appreciation learning. This literature appreciation can be in the form of reading literary

works such as poetry, retelling literary works such as fairy tales: legends, fables, in addition, re-enacting a literary work such as drama, and many others. Creative contents on YouTube can be used as a reference source for students. YouTube is not something that is difficult for students to access. Additionally, in the literature appreciation learning, students can be creative and productive in literature subject and publish their work that has been made to YouTube. The results of its publications can be enjoyed and appreciated by the wider community. The use of YouTube is also easy to access, not even limited by space and time. This social media creates an interesting and fun learning atmosphere, especially when literature appreciation learning in the form of fable or legend texts for class VII A students consisting of 38 male students amidst the COVID-19 pandemic. The following is an example of YouTube contents used by teachers for literature appreciation learning.

Figure 1. Examples of creative content for learning appreciation through oral literature on youtube “The Origin of the Gajah Wong River”, the source of our fairy tales.

Figure 2. Examples of creative content for learning literary appreciation through oral literature on youtube “The Legend of Nyi Roro Kidul”, the source of our fairy tales.

Figure 3. Examples of creative content for learning literary appreciation “Fable Text of Rabbits and Turtles” source Riri.

The creative content on YouTube is used by the teacher to provide examples in learning literary appreciation, especially fable and legend texts. This content is a breakthrough to anticipate learning during this covid-19 pandemic. This learning is expected to foster ideas and creativity that our enthusiasm for learning literary appreciation cannot be hindered by anything, such as during this pandemic.

Conclusion

Teaching and learning activities amidst COVID-19 pandemic are required to be more innovative and creative. The selection of the right learning model can support the process of distance teaching and learning activities. The blended learning model is chosen to support the maximization of the literature appreciation learning process (fable or legend text) for class VII A students in MTS Al Ma'had An-Nur. The blended learning model combines offline and online learning activities. The forum for these two learning activities is through the Google Classroom, WhatsApp group, and creative contents on YouTube. Literature appreciation learning (fable or legend texts) used the blended learning model through three basic stages. These stages are useful so that learning to write short stories can be understood easily by students. The stages in the model, namely: seeking of information, acquisition of information and synthesizing knowledge. Literature appreciation learning activities for class VII A students in MTS Al Ma'had An-Nur using the blended learning model have various advantages. Both educators and students are required to be more independent in using information technology for maximizing teaching and learning activities. The student learning activities carried out remotely in literature appreciation learning are also not boring. This activity is also considered to be very effective in breaking the transmission of COVID-19 with the teaching and learning process through a combination of offline and online learning.

Conflicts of interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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